

Alkaloids of *Mitragyna parvifolia* (Roxb) Korth. and their Transformations

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From the basic fractions of the leaves of *Mitragyna parvifolia* (Roxb) Korth. three oxindole alkaloids, mitraphylline, isomitraphylline and speciophylline N_b-oxide were isolated. A novel method has been developed for the transformation of mitraphylline, the major alkaloid of this species, to the corresponding heteroyohimbinoïd base, ajmalicine without disturbing any chiral centre. Mitraphylline N_b-methoïdide, when treated with triethyloxonium fluoroborate, was converted to its corresponding imino-ether which on reduction with sodium borohydride in acetic acid furnished ajmalicine N_b-methoïdide. The latter could be transformed to ajmalicine by conventional procedure.

THE growing family of oxindole alkaloids has gained much importance on biogenetic grounds and also for the interesting chemical reactions displayed by them. These basic constituents originate from the alkaloids of secoyohimbane or heteroyohimbane series through the intermediacy of the corresponding indoleninium derivatives. The indoleninium intermediates on hydroxylation at the neighbouring carbon (C₂) (vide Chart 1) followed by the abstraction of the proton from the hydroxyl with the concomitant migration of C₂-C₃ bond at C₇ generate the oxindole derivatives. The key role in this transformation is played by the indolic nitrogen N_a. These alkaloids have been reported to occur in *Aspidosperma*, *Mitragyna*, *Ourouparia*, (*Uncaria*), *Rauwolfia* and *Vinca* species and bear a close structural resemblance to each other and possess the same basic framework (having C₂-C₃ bond cleavage) derived from tryptophan via its decarboxylation product tryptamine and secologanin, a C₁₀-unit of terpenoid origin.

Chart-1

In recent years, intensive research is being pursued in this area and this has culminated in the isolation of many new oxindoles, several of these

being stereomers having different configurations. Meaningful allocation of correct conformation of each configuration has been possible from spectral data (viz., pmr spectra) as spectral parameters are conformation-dependent.

The present communication is mainly concerned with the isolation of speciophylline N_b-oxide from *Mitragyna parvifolia* (Roxb) Korth. and the development of a new method for the conversion of mitraphylline, the major alkaloid of this species, to the corresponding heteroyohimbinoïd base with the retention of chirality of the molecule. The genus *Mitragyna* is widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions. Several *Mitragyna* species, which are large trees indigenous to South Eastern Asia, find commercial use in the timber and paper industries. The special feature of this genus is the ability to produce a large number of oxindole alkaloids having pentacyclic structures of ajmalicine type. *M. parvifolia* (Roxb) Korth. is a much investigated species and special mention may be made about the contribution of Shellard and his coworkers¹⁻³ towards systematic chemotaxonomic studies of this genus. From this particular plant occurrence of five alkaloids, viz., mitraphylline (1), pteropodine (2), isopteropodine (3), speciophylline (4) and uncarine F (5) (vide Chart 2) has been reported. It has been observed that environmental factor has a vital role to play in modifying the alkaloid content and the structure. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study the basic constituents of *M. parvifolia* which grows profusely in Bengal plain. The primary objective was to isolate mitraphylline (1), the major alkaloid of *M. parvifolia* and to evolve a new method for its conversion to pentacyclic heteroyohimbane system with the retention of configuration at the asymmetric centres as previously mentioned.

With this object, the leaves of this species were collected from the Indian Botanic Garden, Sibpur, West Bengal. The basic fractions of the alcoholic extract of the leaves yielded three oxindoles of which two were isomeric and already known

in the literature⁴. These were identified as mitraphylline (1) $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_4$ (M^+ 368), m.p. 265-7° and isomitraphylline (6) $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_4$, m.p. 122-3° (vide Chart -), the oxindoles of normal series (D/E ring

the minor differences existing in relative peak intensities only. This observation clearly indicated that it is an N_b -oxide ($C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_5$) of the base having the composition $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_4$.

Chart-2

junction being *trans*) having 15α H- 20β H- 19β H configuration. From the conformational analysis mitraphylline (1) was shown to be a stronger base than the other isomer (6). This is due to the proximity of the lactam carbonyl group to N_b which forms the ammonium ion on protonation. The protonated species has the unique advantage of undergoing stabilisation by H-bonding with the lactam carbonyl group. This situation is not permitted in isomitraphylline. The third oxindole alkaloid was found to be an N_b -oxide of speciohylline (4) previously obtained from *Uncaria*⁵ species only in trace amount. Thus the spectral investigations of the natural product were not possible which could only be studied with the synthetic one. In this communication we would like to report the physical properties of speciohylline N_b -oxide isolated from *M. parvifolia*. The compound was obtained in adequate quantity, thus permitting detailed studies of the molecule. It could be isolated as an amorphous solid, m.p. 113-5° from 10% methanolic chloroform eluates. The most significant feature of this base was its highly polar character and its resistance to migration on chromatoplates [R_f 0.65, developing system MeOH-Et₃NH (12 : 1)]. It showed characteristic oxindole colour reaction—spraying chromatoplate with a solution of 0.2 M FeCl₃ in 85% HClO₄, followed by heating the plates at 90° for 1 hr when a pink spot developed. Its mass spectrum showed a ready loss of 16 mass units generating the base peak at m/e 368 from the molecular ion peak at m/e 384. The remaining fragmentation pattern was practically the same as that of mitraphylline and isomitraphylline,

The compound exhibited absorption maxima at λ_{max}^{EtOH} 220, 245 and 286 nm ($\log \epsilon$: 3.85, 4.01 and 3.23, respectively) similar to those of mitraphylline⁴. The ir spectrum also indicated its structural similarity with heteroyohimbinoid oxindole alkaloids excepting the appearance of an additional peak at 950 cm^{-1} owing to the presence of aliphatic N-oxide. The 90 MHz pmr spectrum of the compound studied in d_6 -DMSO showed a three proton singlet at δ 3.20 attributed to the methyl group of the carbomethoxy function. The C_{17} -H resonated as a singlet at δ 7.50 whereas C_{19} -H as a multiplet ($J_1=6.5$ Hz and $J_2=1.5$ Hz) at δ 4.35 with C_{19} -CH₃ as three proton doublet ($J_1=6.5$ Hz) at δ 1.22.

All these data indicate the compound to be an oxindole base with a heterocyclic ring E, stereoisomeric with mitraphylline. The exact position of C_{19} -CH₃ signal had been used to deduce the nature of D/E ring junction. Heteroyohimbine alkaloids with a *cis* D/E ring junction normally show doublets owing to C_{19} -CH₃ at δ 1.32-1.42 whereas those with *trans* D/E junction exhibit the corresponding signal at δ 1.16-1.19. It appeared that a similar criterion would also be valid in the ring E hetero-oxindole series, since the alkaloids with a *cis* D/E ring junction showed the doublets at δ 1.23-1.4 while those with a *trans* D/E junction showed the corresponding signal at δ 1.1-1.16 (the C_{19} -CH₃ of mitraphylline appearing at δ 1.16). The coupling constant values for C_{19} -H as observed in this case clearly indicated the α -orientation of C_{19} -CH₃ in either heterooxindole having *cis* or *trans* D/E ring junction. The four aromatic

protons in this alkaloid resonated as a multiplet around δ 6.84-7.30 indicating that the oxygen at N_b is on the opposite side of the molecule to C_9-H , otherwise the latter would have separately appeared downfield as a clear one proton doublet. All these information revealed that the compound would be an N_b -oxide of either mitraphylline (1) or speciophylline (4). Mitraphylline (1) was converted to its N_b -oxide derivative on treatment with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid and the product was found to be different from our alkaloid. Interestingly, the natural N_b -oxide of the base when reduced with H_2 -Pd/C in ethanol and also with sulphurous acid was found to be identical with speciophylline (4). The identity of our alkaloid with speciophylline N_b -oxide was subsequently established by comparison with an authentic sample.

Since mitraphylline (1) could be isolated in appreciable quantity it was intended to develop a suitable method to convert it into the corresponding indole (tetrahydro β -carboline) derivative, ajmalicine (7), with the retention of chirality of the molecule. The method reported in the literature⁶ for converting the oxindoles to the corresponding tetrahydro β -carboline derivative was to prepare the N_a -imino-ether from the oxindole with the strong electrophile $Et_3O^+ \cdot BF_4^-$ followed by reduction of the imino-ether with sodium borohydride in acetic acid to the corresponding indolic seco-compound. When the cyclisation of ring C occurred the process ended up with C_3 -epimers. Our objective was to generate the tetrahydro β -carboline derivative from the imino-ether with the retention of configuration at C_3 .

To fulfil this requirement it was necessary to prevent participation of lone pair of electrons on N_b leading to the formation of seco-compound. Hence the basic nitrogen of mitraphylline was quaternised with CH_3I in dry THF, when mitraphylline N_b -methoiodide (8), $C_{22}H_{27}N_2O_4I$, d.p. 260° separated out as a white solid in the reaction medium. This quaternary salt was subsequently treated with dry methylene chloride solution of $Et_3O^+ \cdot BF_4^-$ under an oxygen free dry nitrogen blanket. The imino-ether derivative (9) thus obtained, was then subjected to reduction with sodium borohydride and glacial acetic acid to yield a single product $C_{22}H_{27}N_2O_3I$ (10), d.p. 235°. The product showed ultraviolet absorption maxima at λ_{max}^{OH} 270 and 288 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.9 and 3.75, respectively) similar to those of quaternary heteroyohimbinoïd alkaloid⁷. The identity of the compound with ajmalicine N_b -methoiodide was finally established by comparing their co-tlc behaviour, ultraviolet absorption characteristics and superimposable infrared spectra. The methoiodide was converted to ajmalicine (7), $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_3$ (M^+ 352), m.p. 256°, uv λ_{max}^{OH} 226, 282 and 290 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.64, 3.96 and 3.88, respectively) following the procedure of Karrer⁷. The identity of the base was established by comparison with authentic ajmalicine following the conventional procedure. The sequence of the aforesaid reactions is displayed in Chart 3.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in a Kofler block and are uncorrected. The ultraviolet absorption spectra were recorded in a Carl-Zeiss VSU-1 Universal spectrophotometer in 95% aldehyde free ethanol and the infrared spectra in a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer in KBr disc. The nmr spectra were recorded in a 90 MHz Brücker Spectrospin machine. The solvents were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Column chromatography was carried out with Brockmann alumina and thin layer chromatography with silica gel G. The spots on the chromatoplates were detected by spraying Dragendorff's reagent.

Isolation of mitraphylline, isomitraphylline and speciophylline N_b -oxide: Finely pulverised dry leaves (10 Kg) of *Mitragyna parvifolia* (Roxb) Korth. were extracted with ethanol for three weeks. The ethanolic extract was then concentrated and churned with 5% aqueous citric acid for 72 hr. The neutral portion was separated and filtered off. The filtrate was basified with liquor ammonia in an ice-cold condition. The liberated base was taken up in chloroform, washed with water and dried. The chloroform concentrate was chromatographed over

Brockmann alumina and the column was eluted with solvents of increasing polarities.

The benzene-chloroform (3 : 1) and the chloroform eluates yielded mitraphylline, $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_4$ (M^+ 368), m.p. 265-7°, and isomitraphylline, $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_4$ (M^+ 368), m.p. 122-3°, respective y. From the 10% methanolic chloroform eluates speciophylline N_b -oxide, $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_5$ (M^+ 384), m.p. 183-5° separated and crystallised as white flakes from the same solvent mixtures. UV : $\lambda_{m\alpha\alpha}^{EtOH}$ 220, 245 and 286 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.85, 4.01 and 3.23, respectively). IR : $\nu_{m\alpha\alpha}^{KBr}$ 3400, 1710, 1610, 950 cm^{-1} . PMR in d_6 -DMSO : δ 1.22 (3H, d, $J_1=6.5$ Hz, $C_{19}-CH_3$), 3.20 (3H, s, $-CO_2CH_3$), 4.35 (1H, dm, $J_1=6.5$ Hz and $J_2=1.5$ Hz, $C_{19}-H$), 6.87-7.30 (4H, m, aromatic protons), 7.50 (1H, s, $C_{17}-H$). MS: m/e 384 (M^+), 368 (M-16), 223, 222, 208, 159, 146, 145, 144, 130 and 69.

Preparation of mitraphylline N_b -oxide : To a solution of mitraphylline (10 mg) in dry chloroform was added a solution of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in the same solvent. The temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 0° for 3 hr. The resulting mitraphylline N_b -oxide was isolated by preparative tlc.

Reduction of speciophylline N_b -oxide : a) The natural N_b -oxide (2 mg) was dissolved in spectral alcohol and hydrogenated over Pd/C for 2 hr. The reaction product on filtration and subsequent removal of the solvent furnished the parent oxindole speciophylline, confirmed by co-tlc with an authentic sample. b) The natural N_b -oxide (2 mg) was treated with 5% sulphurous acid and the mixture was allowed to stand for 1 hr. The tertiary base was extracted with chloroform after the solution was made alkaline with ammonia, washed and dried. The chloroform was removed and the residue was found to be identical with an authentic sample of speciophylline.

Preparation of mitraphylline N_b -methoiodide : To a solution of mitraphylline (100 mg) in dry THF (250 ml) methyl iodide (10 ml) was added and the reaction was stirred for 4 hr and kept overnight in the dark. Mitraphylline N_b -methoiodide, $C_{22}H_{27}N_2O_4I$, d.p. 260°, separated out as white amorphous solid (90 mg). Found : C, 51.65; H, 5.35; N, 5.40. $C_{22}H_{27}N_2O_4I$ requires C, 51.76; H, 5.29; N, 5.49%.

Preparation of imino-ether of mitraphylline N_b -methoiodide : To a well-stirred solution of triethyl-oxonium fluoroborate (3.5 g) in dry methylene chloride (25 ml) a solution of mitraphylline N_b -methoiodide (90 mg) in the same solvent (25 ml) was added dropwise under a completely dry and oxygen free nitrogen blanket, stirring being continued for 10 hr.

The reaction mixture was neutralised with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate in ice-cold condition. The methylene chloride layer was separated, washed and dried. Removal of the solvent yielded a gummy mass which on trituration with dry ether afforded the desired imino-ether of the methoiodide (60 mg), $C_{24}H_{31}N_2O_4I$, d.p. 215°. Found : C, 53.45; H, 5.70; N, 5.25. $C_{24}H_{31}N_2O_4I$ requires C, 53.53; H, 5.76; N, 5.20%.

Reduction of the imino-ether of mitraphylline N_b -methoiodide to ajmalicine N_b -methoiodide : The above imino-ether (60 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and sodium borohydride (500 mg) was added portionwise to the solution, kept at a low temperature. After the effervescence ceased, the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 10 hr and later basified with liquor ammonia. The liberated base was taken up in chloroform (3 × 30 ml), washed and dried. On removal of the solvent a gummy residue was obtained. On trituration with dry ether the residue solidified (20 mg), $C_{22}H_{27}N_2O_5I$, d.p. 235°. UV $\lambda_{m\alpha\alpha}^{EtOH}$: 270 and 288 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.9 and 3.75, respectively). Found : C, 53.35; H, 5.53; N, 5.75. $C_{22}H_{27}N_2O_5I$ requires C, 53.44; H, 5.46; N, 5.66%.

Conversion of ajmalicine N_b -methoiodide to ajmalicine : Ajmalicine N_b -methoiodide obtained above was heated in a sealed tube under vacuum at 220-25° for 10 min. The residue was taken up in chloroform. Ajmalicine (yield 25%) crystallised from ether, $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_5$ (M^+ 352), m.p. 252°. UV : $\lambda_{m\alpha\alpha}^{EtOH}$ 226, 282 and 290 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.64, 3.96 and 3.88, respectively). Its identity was established by comparison with an authentic sample by co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are accorded to Dr. J. D. Phillipson, the School of Pharmacy, University of London, U. K., for comparing natural speciophylline N_b -oxide with an authentic sample and to U.G.C. (Delhi) for financial assistance.

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